

The interdisciplinary method of teaching literature at secondary school: applications in the Kenyan classroom

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to determine the benefits of the interdisciplinary method of teaching literature at the secondary school. It seeks to establish areas of possible cooperation between the teachers of other subjects and the teacher of literature for the purpose of enriching the teaching of literature.

Interdisciplinary teaching is one of the newer instructional techniques espoused by progressive researchers on learning and the human brain. It finds support in the pioneering work of such philosophers as Piaget, Dewey and Bruner. These philosophers advocate a constructivist view of learning whereby learners actively participate in acquiring knowledge by building on prior experiences and by establishing connections between experiences. Interdisciplinary teaching helps learners to make connections between learning experiences encountered in different subject areas of the school curriculum thereby expanding their knowledge base.

Key words: innovative techniques, curriculum integration, interdisciplinary teaching.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The declining student achievement in English, which includes Literature in an integrated course, among other key subjects at secondary school has been a cause of concern to teachers, parents and government of Kenya officials alike. Being not only a service subject through which all other non-language subjects in our schools are taught, but also our nation's official language, and an important international language, the poor performance in English raises serious concerns, not only about the quality of passes in the other subjects, but also our school leavers' communicative competence. The Minister of Education in 2002 spoke for many people when he lamented the declining performance in English and Kiswahili while releasing the KCSE results in February 2002. He voiced similar concern regarding the Kenya Certificate of Primary Education, KCPE, saying the results for the same year showed a similar trend. He then observed:

I would like the education ministry's inspectorate division and teachers of these subjects to work towards improving performance. I believe this is an achievable goal. (Quoted in the *Daily Nation*, Tuesday, February 26, 2002).

A columnist on educational issues [1], also expressed the worries of many Kenyans when he observed:

...the way English is taught leaves a lot to be desired if the kinds of letters that the employers get are anything to go by. Most school leavers are unable to construct intelligible sentences even in a 200-word application letter.

The Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) English examination reports regarding the performance in English present a dismal scenario. [2] Observes that:

A quick glance at the means indicates that the performance was not impressive. This is a trend that must be checked and efforts made to improve the situation, given the central position English language occupies in the curriculum, and for the sake of improving the performance.

The situation is not any better in the subsequent years, which yielded similar reports. [2] Asserts that:

Judging by some of the examination scripts that land in the council's marking rooms one can say that some of the candidates are virtually illiterate and they can hardly communicate.

The recent years have shown little improvements according to the [2] reports as shown in Table 1, See also Figure 1.

The results of the year 2000 [2] KCSE examination show dismal performance in English. 66,163 out of 178,608 or 37% of the candidates scored 'D' or below in the subject. Compared even to mathematics, Biology and Chemistry there were fewer candidates who scored A- and above in English. While only 1,140 candidates had A- and above in English, 3,754 had similar grades in Mathematics and 4,518 in Chemistry. The results of the following two years, 2001 and 2002, were worse, with mean marks of 34.575% and 29.61 %, respectively.

Perhaps this is what prompted Kenya's then minister of education to observe, "There is need for an urgent intervention to curb the repeated decline in performance in languages" [3].

The results of the 2005 KCSE examinations indicate that a mere 554 candidates who sat for these examinations managed to achieve the 'A' grade in English. Subjects that are traditionally regarded as 'difficult' returned better scores. For instance, Math (3,644 As), Biology (4,216 As), Physics (3,062 As) and Chemistry (7,116 As). Source [2].

The fact that students can perform so poorly in English, yet perform relatively well in other subjects which rely on English for their teaching, is rather intriguing. What is even more baffling is that, unlike other subjects, one cannot convincingly argue that there is a lack of adequate teaching facilities for English in schools. Apart from the approved textbooks for the subject, other reading materials and opportunities that can be used for practising the skills of the language in a variety of contexts and situations are in abundance. Textbooks in most subject areas and other written materials found in our schools are in English. This aside, it is only in this subject that the students get maximum exposure since, whereas they are exposed to the other subjects only during lessons specifically assigned to those subjects, one expects that their full time linguistic interactions while in school are in English.

Due to the persistently poor results in KCSE English examinations in spite of the abundance of formal and informal teaching resources and practice opportunities, concern has been raised that teachers' instructional strategies, competence and resourcefulness in schools may be wanting. Mbiti, at one time Kenya's Chief Inspector of Schools raises such concerns in a statement contained in [4]:

The burden of improving student's English rests entirely on the shoulders of the teacher of English, whereas the meaningful contexts, which can motivate learners to use language in hypothesizing, generalizing, and showing ideas about common experiences, occur naturally and more often across the curriculum in various subjects.

Mbiti's views tally with those of researchers on the teaching of English as a Second Language. [5] Observe:

Language teachers badly need the help and interest of the teachers of all the other

subjects in the curriculum. With their active cooperation an English course may be very successful, but without it, it cannot be. As soon as pupils spot that correctness and fluency in speech and writing matter only to the English teacher, and that the Biology, Physics and Mathematics staff are happy to decipher the ungrammatical and interpret the inaudible, they will consciously practise correct language habits only in English lessons and the English teacher is practically wasting his time and theirs.

In an attempt to redress the above situation it is the researcher's view that more attention has to be given to pedagogy and teacher input. In this regard Wallah Bin Wallah, a Kiswahili author, amply supports the researcher. Speaking during a workshop for teachers in July 2003, Wallah observed that most teachers were unable to adopt research findings on teaching, preferring to dwell on old training methods. He argued that unless teachers were helped to adopt modern teaching trends geared to academic excellence exam failures would persist. In his words:

Teachers need to update their skills in accordance with the changing trends to meet student demands. Those who wallow in ignorance can therefore not be equal to the job. (Quoted in the *Daily Nation*, Thursday, July 24, 2003).

The Chairman of the Kenya Secondary Schools Head Teachers' Association, Mr. Peterson Muthathai, seems to echo Bin Wallah's sentiments while commenting on the poor 2005 KCSE English and Kiswahili results. He observed:

We call upon the Government to organize in-service training for teachers, especially in Languages, to prepare them adequately to handle the subjects. (Quoted in the *Daily Nation*, Thursday March 2, 2006).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To determine the benefits of the interdisciplinary approach to the teaching of literature at the secondary school.
- 2) To make recommendations and suggestions about possible cooperation between teachers of specific subjects and the teacher of literature for the purpose of enriching the teaching of literature.

Table 1

Year	Mean score in %
1995	55.77
1996	63.79
1997	69.27
1998	63.24
1999	62.42
2000	52.81
2001	34.58
2002	29.61

LEGEND: Students’ performance in English in KCSE from 1995-2002
 (Source: KNEC reports)

Figure 1:
LEGEND: Bar chart showing students’ performance in English in KCSE from 1995-2002.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) What is interdisciplinary teaching?
- 2) What are the benefits of the interdisciplinary method of teaching literature at secondary school level?
- 3) What are the areas of possible cooperation between teachers of specific subjects and the teacher of literature for the purpose of enriching the teaching of literature?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Subjects on the secondary school curriculum are naturally interdependent. Various subjects contain valuable information that can be used to shed light on and explain issues in other subjects. Various subjects can support, and supplement each other in terms of content information. According to [6] any given subject in the school's curriculum is not an isolated body of knowledge. It has relationships with other subjects in the school's curriculum system. An awareness of this should enable the teacher to draw from other subject disciplines in order to enhance learning of the material planned for any particular lesson in any one given subject discipline.

The study's findings, it is hoped, would be used as the basis for interventions aimed at improving the teaching practices relating to Literature in Kenyan secondary schools as one way of raising student achievement. The onus is on teachers, teacher-trainers and policy makers on curriculum design to decide on how best findings of this study would be used as the foundation for instructional and curricular reform for the common goal of enhancing student learning which could in turn translate into improved performance at KCSE.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This paper is based on original research that was carried out conscientiously by the author. The required permits, authorizations and letters of introduction were sought and granted before the data gathering was undertaken. Strict fidelity to facts has been observed in the laying out of the findings and in the discussion. All citations have been properly referenced.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study drew inspiration from General Systems Theory. General Systems Theory came into being as a response to the need for a coherent dialogue between the specialized theories of the various disciplines (Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Psychology, Sociology, and Economics etc.

It was observed that the advance of knowledge in specialized disciplines was increasingly becoming the preserve of specialists in those disciplines to the exclusion of all others; including fellow specialists in other disciplines.

There was concern that knowledge was increasingly being compartmentalized and that the increasingly esoteric language of the specialists in each field meant that they would only be comprehended by fellow specialists in the particular fields. [7] observes:

The reason for this breakup in the body of knowledge is that in the course of specialization the receptors of information themselves become specialized. Hence physicists only talk to physicists, economists to economists – worse still, nuclear physicists only talk to nuclear physicists and econometricians to econometricians.

General Systems Theory aims at pointing out the similarities in the theoretical constructions of different disciplines, where these exist, and to develop theoretical models having applicability to at least two different fields of study. It also aims at constructing a spectrum of theories (a system of systems) which may perform the functions of a "gestalt", a unified "whole."

General Systems Theory seeks to bridge the chasms between the disciplines by developing a framework of general theory, which would enable one specialist to catch relevant communication from others. [7]:

The spread of specialized deafness means that someone who ought to know something that someone else knows is not able to find it out for lack of generalized ears. It is one of the main objectives of General Systems Theory to develop these generalized ears, and by developing a framework of general theory to enable one specialist to catch relevant communication from others. Thus the economist who realizes the strong formal similarity between utility theory in economics and field theory in physics is probably in a better position to learn from the physicists than one who does not.

General Systems Theory provides an excellent model on which to pattern a method of looking at

the various subjects on the secondary school syllabus as comprising a 'gestalt', a "system" with discernible complementary relationships between its parts (the individual subjects). Such a system would:

- i) Encourage dialogue, comparison, sharing and dissemination of knowledge and methods across disciplines.
- ii) Shed light on areas of similarity and possible cooperation between disciplines previously viewed as being mutually exclusive.

When the subjects that comprise the secondary school curriculum are viewed as a 'system' they naturally lend themselves to interdisciplinary teaching as the method most appropriate for establishing the links between the disciplines and hence conveying from one to the other select content as may be required to enrich the ideas in either for the benefit of learners.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Interdisciplinary teaching

Interdisciplinary teaching is often used synonymously with curriculum integration. [8] Describes interdisciplinary teaching as "a knowledge view and curricular approach that consciously applies methodology and language from more than one discipline to examine a central theme, issue, problem, topic or experience."

The organizational structure of interdisciplinary teaching is called a theme, thematic unit, or unit, which is a framework with goals/outcomes that specify what students are expected to learn as a result of the experiences and lessons that are a part of the unit.

The rationale for interdisciplinary teaching

Interdisciplinary teaching is often seen as a way to address some of the recurring problems in education; such as fragmentation and isolated skills instruction. It is seen as a way to support goals such as transfer of learning, teaching students to think and reason, and providing a curriculum more relevant to students [9], [10].

Progressive educational thought is decidedly against the artificial fragmentation of knowledge, preferring more connected learning and coherence in the curriculum.

Benefits of interdisciplinary teaching

(a) Applies, integrates and transfers knowledge

According to [11], while students are learning the basic information in core subject areas, they are learning to apply their knowledge effectively in thinking and reasoning. Interdisciplinary teaching provides a meaningful way in which students can use knowledge learned in one context as a knowledge base in other contexts in and out of school [12].

Many of the important concepts, strategies and skills taught in the language arts are "portable" [13]. They transfer readily to other content areas. The concept of perseverance, for example, may be found in literature and science. Strategies for monitoring comprehension can be directed to reading materials in any content areas. Causes – and - effect relationships exist in literature, science and social studies. Interdisciplinary teaching supports and promotes this transfer. Critical thinking can be applied in any discipline.

(b) Increases motivation

Interdisciplinary teaching can increase students' motivation for learning and their level of engagement. In contrast to learning skills in isolation, when students participate in interdisciplinary experiences they see the value of what they are learning and become more actively engaged [14].

(c) Improves learning

Interdisciplinary teaching provides the conditions under which effective learning occurs. Students learn more when they use the language arts skills to explore what they are learning, write about what they are learning and interact with their classmates and teachers [15].

FINDINGS, DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Subjects on the Kenya school curriculum that have relationships with literature include History and Government, Social Education and Ethics (S.E.E.), Fasihi ya Kiswahili, English language, Christian Religious Education (C.R.E.), Music, Kiswahili (Lugha), and Geography. It is noteworthy that the relationship between English as a subject taught at school and literature is intrinsic and complementary. Mastery of the English language part of the course is instrumental to the understanding of any literary material, be it poetry, drama or prose.

A lot of history is integrated into literary work. There are novels, plays and poems, dealing with what happened in the past, for instance the 'MAU

MAU' war of liberation in Kenya, and students would understand the work better if a History teacher explained the events to them. In this regard, History provides the background information necessary to understand the literary work. A novel like Chinua Achebe's "A man of the people" would be more effectively taught and better understood if the literature teacher had sufficient knowledge from History on colonial and post-colonial African states.

Again, what may be studied in prose, drama or poetry may have a parallel with the history of a people as far as culture and religion are concerned. For instance, the poem 'Omukiga bridegroom's emissary' [16] is resonant with the cultural values of a people concerning courtship, marriage and kinship ties. Francis Imbuga's *Aminata* is a play based on the Luhya people's cultural values regarding the roles of male/female children (i.e. sons and daughters) in the family. History also contributes significantly to the understanding of oral literature genres like legends, myths, songs and proverbs most of which allude to (and carry) actual historical content. The two subjects, C.R.E and S.E.E, provide standards against which to measure the responses and actions of characters in plays, novels, oral narratives and short stories when confronted by moral dilemmas and other situations which demand making difficult decisions and choices.

The play *Aminata* [17] borrows a lot from C.R.E core content namely the place of women in both traditional African society, and the Bible. It also makes reference to the role of religion in African society. In S.E.E, Students learn the ideal character traits and ethics through poems, oral narratives, drama etc. Further, the songs, (Songs of Solomon), poems (psalms) and proverbs found in the Bible and which form C.R.E core content can be an invaluable contribution to literature lessons. Also to be found in Bible are teachings on morality as well as character traits and actions of prominent characters all of which can be used as a standard by which to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of characters in plays, novels, oral narratives and short stories. Again, in C.R.E, the creation stories told by different communities find parallels in such literary genres as myths and legends.

Geography can be used as a resource subject to explain the setting of a play, novel or even short story. The same subject can be used to explain the economic activities of the people in these genres. Kiswahili (Fasihi and Lugha) parallel English language and literature. They can and do

complement each other in as far as the four skills namely reading, writing, speaking and listening are concerned. Material can be used to teach either of the two subject areas (after suitable translations have been made). As for music, it can effectively be used as a tool for teaching metrical patterns in poetry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings of the study, these recommendations are made:

1. The interdisciplinary method should be stressed upon during the training of teachers in colleges. This is necessary so that the spirit of cooperation and teamwork vital to successful interdisciplinary teaching is nurtured early when the teachers are still impressionable.
2. The interdisciplinary method should be promoted and "marketed" during in-service workshops and seminars for teachers. A collective responsibility in teaching should be emphasized at such get-togethers.
3. More teachers should be assigned the various subjects at school in order to ease the pressure on the teachers already attending to the teaching of those subjects. This would in turn lead to adequate time for interaction among teachers necessary for the exchange of ideas; a vital requirement for successful interdisciplinary teaching.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper is derived from the thesis that was submitted by the author in partial fulfillment of the requirements for award of the Master of Philosophy (MPhil) degree in Educational Communication and Technology of Moi University, Kenya.

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